

Models of sustainable uses of energy for just transition environmental Policies: a Theoretical and Empirical Investigation

Carlo Andrea Bollino^{a}*

^a *Department. of Economics (UNIPG)*

** Corresponding Author*

Keywords:

1. DSGE
2. Experiment Design
3. Environmental Awareness
4. just transition environmental Policies (up to 6)

Main ERC field

SH1 - Social Sciences and Humanities

SH1_12 Environmental economics; resource and energy economics; agricultural economics

2. SH1_7 Behavioural economics; experimental economics; neuro-economics

Introduction (max 100 words)

This research project contributes to the study of advanced theoretical and quantitative methods for modeling the sustainable uses of energy, providing the necessary knowledge basis for the implementation of environmental policies. A micro founded dynamic stochastic general equilibrium (DSGE) model with endogenous climate change damage is constructed. The model is MOSETEP: Model of Sustainable uses of Energy for just Transition Environmental Policies. This tool is used to analyze the determinants of agents' environmental awareness (EA) of agents, to understand how to design policies that are better accepted.

Methods (max 100 words)

This project aims at constructing an innovative DSGE, incorporating the impact of notion of Environmental Awareness (EA) and energy efficiency (EE), from different and complementary dimensions (theoretical, empirical, experimental). The novelties lie in the simultaneous modeling and simulating of: the EA driving consumer attitudes; the firms propensity to invest in energy efficiency; the endogeneity of climate change damage. The model is MOSETEP: Model of Sustainable uses of Energy for just Transition Environmental Policies.

Results (max 100 words)

This project is expected to provide concrete and innovative solutions for issues related to the acceptability of environmental policies (and relative costs) to support the decarbonization and diversification of energy sources in the EU area. The project will be carried out by four research units:

University of Naples "Parthenope" (RUNA), University of Rome "Tor Vergata" (RUTV), University of Perugia, (RUPG), University of Milan (RUMI).

We identify policy suggestions to contribute to the implementation of the PNRR that also strengthens the possibility of success of the decarbonization strategy to 2050 and more generally in fostering the reaching of accessible and safe clean energy system and a just transition.

References (up to 6)

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Funded projects involved

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